

No Genuine Copula in Japanese: the pseudo-copula =*da* as an existential, conjunctive and locative complex¹

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Abstract:

This paper proposes an alternative analysis of the Japanese so-called copula =*da* and its non-contracted form =*de aru*. While =*da* has traditionally been treated as a copula equivalent to English *be*, we argue instead that the nature of the Japanese pseudo-copula can be better understood in terms of **how Japanese, which lacks the primitive *be*, has employed its most basic linguistic resources — namely, the locative postposition =*ni*, the conjunctive suffix -*te* and the existential verb *ar-*, all of which, still today, autonomously underlie =*da* — to encode a relation between an entity and its specification as to what it is.**

Under this conception, the construction $A=wa B=de aru$ — translationally 'A is B' — is analysed semantically as both **existence-introducing** and **existence-domain-specifying** (i.e. conceptual-domain-specifying). Syntactically, it consists of the one-argument obligatory construction $[A=wa aru]$ 'A exists' — despite its apparent counterintuitiveness — and the adjunct $[B=de]$ 'with (A's existence) located in the conceptual domain of B' or, more practically, 'and it is as B'. Schematically, it is representable as the conjunctive proposition $EXIST(A) \wedge IN(evEXIST(A), B)$ — whose default negation pattern is, as expected, scope-limited $EXIST(A) \wedge \neg IN(evEXIST(A), B)$, realised as $A=wa B=de=wa nai$.

This reanalysis makes possible a unified account of the structure, semantics and diachronic development of Japanese so-called copular constructions.

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1. Introduction — morphosyntactic and prosodic separability of *de* and *aru* in *dearu* and syntactic and prosodic constituency of *de* and the preceding NPs

In Japanese linguistics, *da/dearu* has traditionally been treated as a copula equivalent to English *be*, as in (1), where *dearu* can be replaced by *=da*, '=' indicating enclisis:

- (1) kare=wa gakusei dearu
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student(PRED) COP
 'He is a student.'

However, this analysis faces a major challenge: it cannot account for the **high degree of independence between *de* and *aru* in *dearu***. For instance, when the noun phrase (NP) *gakusei* 'student' is marked by the focus/additive enclitic particle *=mo* 'also' — one of the so-called *toritatesi* in Japanese linguistics — the sentence cannot take the expected form shown in (2):

- (2) *kare=wa gakusei =mo **dearu**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student(PRED) also(ADD) COP
 'He is also a student.'

but must be as in (3):

- (3) kare=wa gakusei **de** =mo **aru**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student(PRED) COP? also(ADD) COP?
 'He is also a student.'

The particle *=mo* is inserted between *de* and *aru*, as if it were behaving as an infix from the perspective that treats *dearu* as a single copula — a situation comparable to the adverb *also* being inserted into the copula *is* in English, as in **he i-also-s a student*. Furthermore, in the complex sentence in (4):

- (4) kare=wa gakusei **deari** kanozyo=wa syakaizin **=da**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student(PRED) COP she(SUBJ)=TOP working adult(PRED) COP
 'He is a student, she is a working adult.'

the first *deari* is very frequently reduced to *de* alone, without *ari*, which is, formally, the conjunctive form — namely, the so-called *ren'yōkei* — of the existential verb *aru*, as in (5):

- (5) kare=wa gakusei **de** kanozyo=wa syakaizin **=da**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student(PRED) COP? she(SUBJ)=TOP working adult(PRED) COP
 'He is a student, she is a working adult.'

Prosodically, too, the so-called copula *dearu* exhibits unexpected behaviour. If *dearu* were a single word, it would be expected to constitute either an independent prosodic word (ω) or an enclitic, so the utterance *kare=wa gakusei dearu* would be expected to be prosodised as either (6) or (7), where " | " marks a prosodic-word boundary and prosodic words in Japanese generally correspond to traditional *bunsetsu*:

(6) | *kare=wa* | *gakusei=dearu* | — *dearu* as an enclitic (i.e. encliticised to *gakusei*)

(7) | *kare=wa* | *gakusei* | *dearu* | — *dearu* as an independent ω

In actual speech, nevertheless, the prosodisation is implemented as in (8):

(8) | *kare=wa* | *gakusei=de* | *aru* | — *de* as an enclitic and *aru* as an independent ω

Since prosodic-word boundaries are determined with reference to morphosyntactic information (Nespor & Vogel 2007), the fact that the utterance is prosodised as | *kare=wa* | *gakusei=de* | *aru* | strongly suggests the presence of a morphosyntactic boundary between *de* and *aru* — namely, that *de* and *aru* constitute distinct morphosyntactic elements. This prosodic separation is further supported by the fact that the discourse enclitic particle *=ne* 'you know' — one of the so-called *syūzyōsi* in Japanese linguistics — can intervene between *de* and *aru*, as in (9), which would be impossible if *dearu* constituted a single prosodic word:

(9) | *kare=wa=ne* | *gakusei=de=ne* | *aru=ne* |

All of these facts demonstrate that ***de* and *aru* are morphosyntactically and prosodically separable**, whereas **the NP *gakusei* and *de* are always syntactically and prosodically inseparable**, as illustrated in (10):

(10) *Kare=wa* [*gakusei de*] [*aru*].

Kare=wa [*gakusei de*] *mo* [*aru*].

Kare=wa [*gakusei de*] [*ari*], *kanozyo=wa syakaizin=da*.

Kare=wa [*gakusei de*], *kanozyo=wa syakaizin=da*.

Kare=wa=ne [*gakusei de*]=*ne* [*aru*]=*ne*.

Hence, in *kare=wa gakusei dearu*, the sequence *gakusei=de* is assumed to constitute a both

syntactically and prosodically defined constituent, as Dalla Chiesa (2015) notes: "the NP-*de* element must always be the phrase (in the closest proximity to the verb)"², where the parentheses are added by the present author. This *gakusei=de* is formally identical to that which has been treated as a postpositional phrase (PP) headed by the so-called postposition *=de*. In what follows, therefore, *gakusei=de* will be treated provisionally as a PP. This separation between *=de* and *aru* is compatible with Matsuoka's observation that "the copula *da* consists of the postposition *de* and the verb *aru*" (2019: 142). The fact that *gakusei=de* and *aru* each constitute a separate prosodic word can thus be naturally accounted for.

2. NP + *=de* as a conceptual-locative adjunct ConjP and *aru* as a one-argument existential verb

In Japanese, **phrases of the form [NP + *=de*] generally function as adjuncts**, as Hasegawa (1999: 26, translated from Japanese) states: "The case particle *=de* occurs not only for 'location of an action' but also for a variety of other elements such as 'cause' (*kaze=de yasumu* 'take time off for a cold'), 'means' (*genkin=de kau* 'buy with cash'), 'time' (*mikka=de tukuru* 'make in three days') and 'state' (*hadaka=de odoru* 'dance naked'), and all of these fundamentally function only as adjuncts. There are no predicates that require these as arguments indispensable for their informational completeness. From this, it can be generalised that *=de* marks adjuncts." Based on this generalisation, *kare=wa gakusei=de aru* can be syntactically analysed as consisting of the **obligatory argumental structure [kare=*wa aru*]** and the **adjunctive structure [gakusei=*de*]**. Further justification for analysing *gakusei=de* as an adjunct rather than an argument — despite its apparent counterintuitiveness — will be provided later in this section and in Sections 5 and 8.

In *kare=wa aru*, the verb *aru* — or, more precisely, its stem *ar-* — can thus be analysed as a **ONE-ARGUMENT predicate**, selecting only the NP *kare* as its argument. When *ar-* **functions as a one-argument predicate**, it means 'exist', as in *sono kanōsei=wa aru* 'that possibility exists', *mada kibō=wa aru* 'the hope still exists', *sonna koto=wa ari-e-nai* 'such a thing cannot exist'

² She argues that the ungrammaticality of **neko=de wagahai=ga aru* 'I am a cat' supports her claim that "the NP-*de* element must always be the phrase in the closest proximity to the verb". However, the ungrammaticality of this sentence does not arise from word order, but rather from the fact that *wagahai*, while functioning as a topic, is not marked by the particle *=wa*. Indeed, although fairly awkward, *neko=de wagahai=wa aru* is not completely ungrammatical, and expressions such as NP=*de watasi=wa ari-tai* 'as the referent denoted by the NP I want to exist' — e.g. *ryōsikitekina syakaizin=de watasi=wa ari-tai* 'as a rational member of society I want to exist' — sound much more natural.

and *sore=wa atte=wa nara-nai* 'that must not exist'. Accordingly, the sentence *kare=wa aru* can be interpreted as 'he exists', introducing *kare* as an entity. An *entity* here is understood as a *constituent of any world, actual or not*, rather than as a spatiotemporally instantiated object, and *exist* here is intended in the sense of *being an entity*. (Note that, in Contemporary Japanese, the use of *aru* as a one-argument existential verb often has a somewhat literary or philosophical flavour, as in *ware omou, yueni ware ari* 'I think, therefore I am' or *aru=to iu koto=wa dō iu koto=ka=to iu toi* 'the problem of what it means to exist'. This verb is more commonly used as a two-argument existential or locative verb as in *tukue=no ue=ni hon=ga aru* 'there is a book on the desk' or *hon=wa tukue=no ue=ni aru* 'the book is on the desk'. In everyday registers, the Sino-Japanese — or, *kango* — verb *sonzai-suru* is often preferred for expressing one-argument existential predication.)

This existential meaning is saliently reflected in the commonly used compound nouns *ari-kata* and *ari-yō*, which signify 'mode/manner of existing, ideal way to exist' and 'state/appearance of existing', respectively. Both are formed by combining the stem *ari-* of the verb *aru* in this sense — namely, 'exist' — with the nominal formatives *-kata* 'mode, manner, way' and *-yō* 'state, appearance', respectively. Further justification for analysing *ar-* in this construction as 'exist' — **a meaning that, for informational and pragmatic reasons, is rarely brought to the speaker's or hearer's awareness** in ordinary assertions of the meta-inferential type 'A = B' or 'A ∈ B' — will be presented in Section 6.

As for *gakusei=de*, on the other hand, although **phrases headed by =de** can mark, as mentioned above with reference to Hasegawa (1999: 26), a range of θ -roles such as location, cause, means, time or state, the interpretation adopted here for the present construction is **locative**, namely the primitive sense of *=de*. This use does not mark, however, a physical location but a **conceptual location**. Here, conceptual location refers to locating or anchoring an entity in the sense defined above within a conceptual space structured by domains mutually defined through semiological opposition. Consequently, *gakusei=de* means 'located or anchored in the **conceptual domain** of "student"' or, more practically, 'as a student'. A conceptual domain is a **category construed as a locus in which entities are located**. A category here is a **conceptual grouping of entities viewed as sharing common features, as constructed by human cognitive processes**. Put simply, a category here exists only as a construct of the human mind. Whether a category contains a single member or multiple ones is irrelevant. Even when *B* is a proper noun in the construction *A=wa B=de aru*, *B* signifies a conceptual domain corresponding to a category

defined by the feature of being referable by that proper noun. Likewise, *kimi* 'you' in *watasi=ni totte itiban taisetuna=no=wa kimi=da* 'the most important thing for me is you' is understood as a conceptual domain defined by the category 'the unique addressee in the context of utterance or the speech situation'.

Conceptual space is founded on an **analogy with physical space**. The construction in (11):

(11) *Kare=wa syakaizin=de aru: sigatu=ni gakusei=kara syakaizin=ni natta.*

'He is a working adult: in April, he moved from being a student to being a working adult.'

'(lit.) He exists, and it is **in** the conceptual domain of "working adult": in April, he moved **from** the conceptual domain of "student" **to** that of "working adult".'

indicates that the same entity denoted by *kare* has moved within the conceptual space **from** the domain *gakusei* 'student' **to** the distinct domain *syakaizin* 'working adult', thereby relocating its existence **in** the latter domain. The postpositions *=de* 'in' in *gakusei=de*, *=kara* 'from' in *gakusei=kara* and *=ni* 'to' in *syakaizin=ni* are plausibly understood as **metaphorical extensions of the physical location, source and goal markers**, as in the construction in (12):

(12) *Kare=wa Tōkyō=de hataraitte=iru: sigatu=ni Kyōto=kara Tōkyō=ni yatte=kita.*

'He is working in Tokyo: in April, he came to Tokyo from Kyoto.'

'(lit.) He is working, and it is **in** the physical domain of "Tokyo": in April, he came **from** the physical domain of "Kyoto" **to** that of "Tokyo".'

Given that **constructions encoding conceptual space systematically mirror the constructions encoding physical space** — that is, the **linguistic isomorphism between physical space and conceptual space** — it can be argued that speakers do not intentionally choose a spatial metaphor. Rather, Japanese grammar provides no alternative formal resources, and it therefore appears to formally force conceptual category domains to be treated in spatial terms.

Syntactically and semantically, the core phrasal structure found in *kare=wa gakusei=de aru* can be analysed provisionally as $[_{VP_1} [_{PP} \textit{gakusei=de}] [_{VP_0} \textit{kare ar-}]]$. In the lower VP $[_{VP_0} \textit{kare ar-}]$ 'he exists', the stem *ar-* of the existential verb *aru* and the NP *kare* constitute a one-argument predicate and its theme argument, respectively. In the higher VP $[_{VP_1} [_{PP} \textit{gakusei=de}] [_{VP_0} \textit{kare ar-}]]$ 'he exists, with his existence located in the conceptual domain of "student"', on the other hand, the postposition *=de* — or, more precisely, **the underlying postposition =ni contained within this surface postposition–conjunction complex =de**, as will be discussed below —

behaves as if it were a two-argument predicate, locating the eventuality 'he exists' signified by the lower VP [_{VP} *kare ar-*], within the conceptual domain signified by the adjunctive NP [*gakusei*] 'student'. Semantically, therefore, the construction expresses 'He exists, with his existence located in the conceptual domain of "student"' or, more practically, 'He exists, and it is as a student'. Since the adjunct *gakusei=de* — containing the predicate-like *=ni* within *=de* — is introduced precisely for the latter predication, **the most crucial logical** — albeit not syntactic — **predicate in this construction is not the verbal stem *ar-*** — which only introduces *kare*'s existence in the lower VP [_{VP} *kare ar-*] — but rather **the underlying predicate-like postposition *=ni* contained within the surface postposition–conjunction amalgam *=de*** — which, in the higher VP [_{VP} [_{PP} [*gakusei=de*] [_{VP} [*kare ar-*]]], locates *kare*'s existence signified by the lower VP [_{VP} *kare ar-*] in the conceptual domain signified by the NP [*gakusei*].

Schematically, using the more abstract construction *A=wa B=de aru*, it can be represented as the conjunctive proposition $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$. Here, the conjunct $E(A)$ 'A exists', where E abbreviates EXIST, corresponds to the core construction *A=wa aru*, and the whole proposition $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$ 'A exists, with A's existence located in the conceptual domain of B' corresponds to the whole construction *A=wa B=de aru*. The core construction *A=wa aru* 'A exists', even without *B=de* 'with (A's existence) located in the conceptual domain of B', constitutes the atomic proposition $E(A)$, since *B=de* is assumed here to be adjunctive. Thus, the first conjunct $E(A)$ **introduces A's existence**, whereas the second conjunct $IN(evE(A), B)$ **specifies as B the conceptual domain in which A's existence is located**. Accordingly, *A=wa B=de aru*, representable as $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$, means **'A exists, with A's existence located in the conceptual domain of B'** or, using the aforementioned Japanese compound nouns, one may say that **A exists** and that **what A's existence is located in**, namely **B**, is **A's *ari-kata*** or **A's *ari-yō***. Thus, any essive reading of *B=de* derives from the very nature of the domain of B, rather than from *=de* itself or from *ar-*.

The notation $E(A)$ designates schematically a linguistic unit *A ar-* constituted by its two inseparable facets — namely, the meaning 'exist- A', that is, the eventuality of A's existence, and the phonological form /ē ar-/ corresponding to it — whereas $evE(A)$ designates only the former facet, that is, the meaning 'exist- A' or the eventuality of A's existence contained in *A ar-*: since $E(A)$ is a predicate-functional representation of the two-facet linguistic unit *A ar-*, the operator *ev* in $evE(A)$ — abbreviated from 'eventuality' — serves to extract only its semantic facet from $E(A)$. Thus, $IN(evE(A), B)$ represents **a semantic relation, at the propositional level, between**

an eventuality and its domain as constructed in the proposition, with a corresponding phonological realisation. Standard predicate-logic notation is not well suited to representing the **routine linguistic operation of locating an eventuality in a domain within the proposition** and the notation $evE(A)$ is adopted only to make that operation explicit. Note that, since $IN(evE(A), B) \Rightarrow E(A)$, it follows that $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B) \equiv IN(evE(A), B)$; hence **$E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$ is logically redundant**, although it is still assumed to be **indispensable for a faithful formalisation of the syntactic–semantic structure of $A=wa B=de aru$** .

Let us return to the adjunctivity of $B=de$ in $A=wa B=de aru$. As will be discussed in Section 7, the contemporary $=de$ originated historically from the sequence $=ni-te$, where $=ni$ is assumed to have functioned as a locative postposition and $-te$ as a conjunctive suffix. The development was probably driven by the deletion of $-i-$ and by postnasal voicing — typical of the Yamato lexical stratum — yielding the sequence $=ni-te \rightarrow *=n-te \rightarrow =n-de \rightarrow =de$. Even today, in phrases of the form $[NP + =de]$, one can observe stylistic variation between the so-called postposition $=de$ and the postposition–conjunction sequence $=ni-te$, as in $Tōkyō=de / Tōkyō=ni-te$ 'in Tokyo', though the latter is a more formal and literal form. Given this diachronic development and the synchronic variation, it is plausible to assume that the underlying form of $B=de$ is still $B=ni-te$, where, strictly speaking, **it is $B=ni$ headed by the underlying postposition $=ni$ that marks conceptual location and the conjunctive suffix $-te$ adjoins $B=ni$, not as an argument but as an adjunct**, to $A=wa aru$ — or more precisely, **to the VP node $[A ar-]$ within $A=wa aru$** .

An NP marked by $=ni$ functioning as an argument is selected by the predicate as an element semantically indispensable for completing its meaning. The link between the predicate and such an argumental $NP=ni$ is determined by the argument structure inherent in the predicate, and is therefore intrinsic and necessary to it. By contrast, an underlying $NP=ni$ functioning as an adjunct is optional for the predicate's meaning, and the link between the adjunct $NP=ni$ and the predicate is extrinsic to and contingent on the predicate. In Contemporary Japanese, this extrinsic and contingent relation needs to be made explicit in a linguistic form, and the device used for this purpose is the conjunctive suffix $-te$. It may be assumed, from a cognitive perspective, that the *conjunctivity* of $-te$ has been metaphorically extended — via the schema of *junctivity* — into *adjunctivity*, as schematised in (13):

Having thus developed into an adjunctive suffix, *-te* adjoins *NP=ni* to the predicate or to some node in the predicate phrase as an adjunct rather than as an argument. The surface realisation of this underlying *NP=ni-te* is *NP=de*. Thus, the use of *=de* as an adjunct marker in Contemporary Japanese can be accounted for by the fact that its underlying form *=ni-te* contains the conjunctive suffix *-te*, which functions adjunctively in this context. Consequently, *B=ni-te*, surfacing as *B=de*, can be analysed not as a PP but as a conjunction phrase (ConjP) headed by the conjunction *-te* with the complement PP *B=ni*, as illustrated in (14):

(14) [_{ConjP} [_{PP} [_{NP} *B*] [_P *=ni*]] [_{Conj} *-te*]]

In the construction *A=wa B=de aru*, therefore, it seems more accurate to characterise *=de* as a **complex consisting of the predicate-like conceptual-locative postposition *=ni* and the adjunctive-conjunction suffix *-te***.

The remaining problem is to determine what element in the linguistic form *A=wa B=de aru* formally corresponds to the operator \wedge , which expresses logical conjunction in the proposition $E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$. The phrasal structure corresponding to the schematic representation $E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$ is assumed to be as in (15), in line with the analysis in (14):

(15) [_{VP_i} [_{ConjP} *B=ni-te*] [_{VP_o} *A ar-*]]

where the lower VP [_{VP_o} *A ar-*] corresponds to the proposition $E(A)$, and the higher VP [_{VP_i} [_{ConjP} *B=ni-te*] [_{VP_o} *A ar-*]] — formed by adjoining the adjunct PP [_{PP} *B=ni*] to the lower VP [_{VP_o} *A ar-*] via the adjunctive-conjunction *-te* — corresponds to the conjunctive proposition $E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$. The semantic composition corresponding to the structure in (15) is given in (16):

(16) [_{NP} <i>A</i>]:	A
[_V <i>ar-</i>]:	E()
[_{VP_o} <i>A ar-</i>]:	E(A)
[_{NP} <i>B</i>]:	B
[_P <i>=ni</i>]:	IN(ev(),)
[_{Conj} <i>-te</i>]:	\wedge
[_{PP} <i>B=ni</i>]:	IN(ev(), B)
[_{ConjP} <i>B=ni-te</i>]:	\wedge IN(ev(), B)
[_{VP_i} [_{ConjP} <i>B=ni-te</i>] [_{VP_o} <i>A ar-</i>]]:	$E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$

In (16), what corresponds to the logical conjunction operator \wedge , which combines the two conjuncts $E(A)$ and $IN(evE(A), B)$, is the adjunctive conjunction $[_{Conj} -te]$. This conjunction $[_{Conj} -te]$ both syntactically adjoins, as stated above, the PP $[_{PP} B=ni]$ to the VP $[_{VP_0} A ar-]$ as an adjunct and, logically, functions as the conjunctive operator \wedge , introducing the most crucial logical — though not syntactic — predicate in this construction $IN(ev(),)$, which is marked by the predicate-like postposition $=ni$. Compositionally, the lower VP $[_{VP_0} A ar-]$ already constitutes an independent proposition $E(A)$ and, by merging this lower VP with the adjunctive ConjP $[_{ConjP} B=ni-te]$, which constitutes $\wedge IN(ev(), B)$, the higher VP $[_{VP_1} [_{ConjP} B=ni-te] [_{VP_0} A ar-]]$ is formed, constituting the conjunctive proposition $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$.

The syntactic derivation corresponding to (16) can be represented as in (17):

(17) $A=wa B=de aru$. '(lit.) A exists, with A's existence located in the conceptual domain B.'

Adjunct	Core construction
$[=ni]$	$[ar-]$
$\rightarrow [B=ni]$	$\rightarrow [A ar-]$
$\rightarrow [[B=ni] -te]$	$\rightarrow [[[B=ni] -te] [A ar-]]$ (adjunct embedding)
	$\rightarrow [[[[B=ni] -te] [A ar-]] -ru]$
	$\rightarrow [[[[[[B=ni] -te] [A ar-]] -ru] Top0\emptyset]$
	$\rightarrow [A_i=wa [[[[[[B=ni] -te] [t_i ar-]] -ru] Top0\emptyset]]]$
	$\rightarrow A=wa B=de ar-u$

In (17), $-ru$ is an inflexional tense suffix specified as $[-past]$; the category Topic, abbreviated as Top in (17), is "a kind of functional category" that "can be considered to embed the IP into discourse and context" (Hasegawa 1999: 91, translated from Japanese), and is assumed in this paper to be realised by the phonologically null morpheme -0 , which we designate as Topic⁰\emptyset, abbreviated as Top⁰\emptyset. The element that moves to the specifier of TopP is assigned the particle $=wa$ and functions to indicate the topic of the sentence. The underlying posposition–conjunction and verb–tense sequences $=ni-te$ and $ar-ru$ surface as $=de$ and $ar-u$, respectively.

In opposition to this $A=wa B=de aru$, the semantically related and syntactically similar but distinct construction $A=wa B=ni aru/iru$ 'A is located in B' — in which $A=wa aru/iru$ 'A is

located', without $B=ni$ 'in B', cannot constitute a proposition, since $B=ni$ is argumental, as discussed in Section 4 — can be represented as $IN(A, B)$, which represents solely the **specification of the physical domain of location**, without explicitly introducing A's existence, which is presupposed in this construction. $IN(A, B)$ thus constitutes an **atomic proposition**. The compositional difference between the conjunctive $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$ and the atomic $IN(A, B)$ is reflected in their default negation patterns, such as the partial or scope-limited negation $A=wa B=de=wa nai$ in the former vs. the total or wide-scoped negation $A=wa B=ni nai/i-nai$ in the latter — namely, $E(A) \wedge \neg IN(evE(A), B)$ vs. $\neg IN(A, B)$ — which will be discussed in Section 8.

Thus, instead of the traditional **copula-based** analysis in (18) = (1), representable as $BE(kare, gakusei)$:

- (18) $kare=wa$ $gakusei$ **dear-u**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student(PRED) **COP-PRES**
 'He is a student.'

in this paper, a **no-copula-based** analysis in (19), representable as $E(kare) \wedge IN(evE(kare), gakusei)$, is adopted, where **CONCEP-LOC** and **CONJ** abbreviate 'conceptual-locative' and 'conjunctive', respectively:

- (19) $kare=wa$ $gakusei=de$ (underlyingly $gakusei=ni-te$) **ar-u**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student=**CONCEP-LOC-CONJ (ADJUNCT)** **exist-PRES**
 'He exists, with his existence located in the conceptual domain of "student".'

Thus, the three fundamental linguistic resources employed in Japanese to encode a relation between an entity and its specification as to what it is are:

- **Predicate-like conceptual-locative postposition =ni 'in'**
- **Adjunctive-conjunction suffix -te 'and'**
- **One-argument existential verb ar- 'exist'**

and the conceptual device used in this paper is their compositional meaning represented by:

- **$E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$**

3. The so-called postposition =*de* as an Adjunctive Eventuality-Domain Specifier: Λ IN(ev(), NP)

In the previous section, the constituent *gakusei=de* in the construction *kare=wa gakusei=de aru* — representable as $\text{EXIST}(kare) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evEXIST}(kare), \text{gakusei})$ — was analysed as the underlying ConjP *gakusei=ni-te*, which corresponds to the logical component Λ IN(ev(), **gakusei**). In this construction, the underlying postposition =*ni* functions conceptual-locatively, and the NP *gakusei* signifies the conceptual domain in which *kare*'s existence is located, as shown in (20):

- (20) *kare=wa* *gakusei=de* (underlyingly *gakusei=ni-te*) *ar-u*
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student=CONCEP-LOC-CONJ (ADJUNCT) exist-PRES
 'He exists, with his existence located in the conceptual domain of "student".'

However, the adjunctive ConjP [NP + =*de*] can function not only conceptual-locatively, as in (20), but also **physical-locatively**, as shown in (21):

- (21) *kare=wa* *Tōkyō=de* (underlyingly *Tōkyō=ni-te*) *hataraitte=i-ru*
 he(SUBJ)=TOP Tokyo=PHYSIC-LOC-CONJ (ADJUNCT) working=be-PRES
 'He is working, with his working located in the physical domain of "Tokyo".'

Thus, the construction *kare=wa Tōkyō=de hataraitte=iru* can be schematically represented as $\text{WORK}(kare) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evWORK}(kare), \text{Tōkyō})$, in parallel to $\text{EXIST}(kare) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evEXIST}(kare), \text{gakusei})$ from *kare=wa gakusei=de aru*.

In both sentences, the underlying postposition =*ni*, representable as $\text{IN}(\text{ev}(), \text{NP})$, within the postposition–conjunction complex =*de* locates the eventualities expressed by the obligatory constructions *kare=wa hataraitte=iru* and *kare=wa aru* — represented by $\text{WORK}(kare)$ and $\text{EXIST}(kare)$, respectively — within the domains signified by the NPs *Tōkyō* and *gakusei*, yielding additional propositions $\text{IN}(\text{evWORK}(kare), \text{Tōkyō})$ and $\text{IN}(\text{evEXIST}(kare), \text{gakusei})$. The underlying conjunction -*te*, representable as Λ , adjoins these eventuality-domain-specifying propositions to the base propositions $\text{WORK}(kare)$ and $\text{EXIST}(kare)$, yielding the conjunctive propositions $\text{WORK}(kare) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evWORK}(kare), \text{Tōkyō})$ and $\text{EXIST}(kare) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evEXIST}(kare), \text{gakusei})$. Accordingly, it can be assumed that the **Japanese postposition–conjunction complex =*de*** — underlyingly =*ni-te* — does not function as a simple locative postposition but can serve as what may be called an **adjunctive eventuality-domain specifier: Λ IN(ev(), NP)**.

aru may reasonably be regarded syntactically — though not informationally or pragmatically, as will be discussed in Section 5 — as a **structurally self-contained, existence-introducing construction** *kare=wa aru* 'he exists', **accompanied by the conceptual-locative adjunct** *gakusei=de* — underlyingly *gakusei=ni-te* — 'with (his existence) located in the conceptual domain of "student"', **which conjunctively specifies the domain of existence**.

Thus, in *A=wa B=de aru*, the constituent *B* signifies a conceptual domain of existence, whereas in *A=wa B=ni aru/iru*, *B* signifies a physical domain of location for the theme. This difference surfaces formally when *B* is replaced by a pro-form. As shown in (26) and (27) below, in the former construction *B* is substituted by the pro-form *sō*, which signifies such notions as property, attribute, characteristic or manner and is glossable as 'so', whereas in the latter construction *B* is substituted by the locative demonstrative pronoun *soko* 'there':

(26) *A=wa B=de aru.* → *A=wa sō=de aru.*

(27) *A=wa B=ni aru/iru* → *A=wa soko=ni aru/iru.*

Although both constructions are assumed to involve a proposition of the form IN(x, y), the formal opposition between *sō* and *soko* reflects whether the second term *y* signifies a conceptual or, alternatively, a physical domain. Note that even when the postposition–conjunction complex *=de* — namely, the eventuality-domain specifier — is used, if *B* in *B=de* signifies a physical domain, it is substituted by *soko*, as in *kare=wa gakkō=de / Tōkyō=de hataraitte=iru* 'he is working in a/the school / in Tokyo' → *kare=wa soko=de hataraitte=iru* 'he is working there'.

5. The syntactic optionality and pragmatic necessity of *B=de* in *A=wa B=de aru*

Although *B=de* — underlyingly *B=ni-te* — in *A=wa B=de aru* is assumed to be **syntactically an adjunct, it cannot be deleted**. This is because, in this construction, **the most crucial logical** — though not syntactic — **predicate is** not the verbal stem *ar-* that introduces *A*'s existence, but rather **the logically predicate-like postposition =ni within the postposition–conjunction complex =de, which locates A's existence in the conceptual domain signified by B**. It is also because the sentence, while structurally consisting of the argumental *A=wa aru* 'A exists' and the adjunctive *B=de* 'with (A's existence) located in the conceptual domain of B' or, more practically, 'and it is as B', functions as a categorical or identificational sentence in which **the**

focus falls on the adjunct *B=de*.

Therefore, the **non-deletability of *B=de*** is assumed to **arise from its informational and pragmatic indispensability** rather than from syntactic necessity. The distinction can be represented as in the following table (28):

(28) Level	Structure	Function
Syntax	[_{VP} <i>A ar-</i>] + [_{ConjP} <i>B=ni-te</i>]	One-argument VP + adjunctive ConjP
Semantics	'A exists, with A's existence located in the conceptual domain of B'	Existence introduction + domain specification $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$
Information Structure	[<i>A=wa aru</i>] + [<i>B=ni-te</i>]	Given + New (default)
Pragmatics	Focus on <i>B=ni-te</i> (default)	Pragmatic obligatoriness and non-deletability of <i>B=de</i> due to focus

The verb *ar-u* is not the only predicate that requires an adjunct for informational and pragmatic reasons. Japanese has a verb meaning 'lead one's life', namely *kurasi-u*. In the natural example in (29), if the physical-locative ConjP *Tōkyō=de* '(and it is) in Tokyo' is deleted, as in (30):

(29) *Kare=wa Tōkyō=de kurasi-te ir-u.* 'He leads his life (and it is) in Tokyo.'

(30) ?*Kare=wa kurasi-te ir-u.* 'He leads his life.'

the resulting sentence is pragmatically infelicitous. One might therefore be tempted to treat the ConjP *Tōkyō=de* as an argument. If *Tōkyō=de* were an argument, the argument structure of the stative verb *kurasi-u* would be [physical domain, agent], where the agent NP refers to an entity that participates in an activity characterisable as a life. However, in (29) the ConjP *Tōkyō=de* can be replaced either by the manner AdvP *siawase-ni* 'happily' or by the comitative PP *kazoku=to* '(lit.) with the family', yielding fully natural results, as in (31) and (32):

(31) *Kare=wa siawase-ni kurasi-te i-ru.* 'He leads his life happily.'

(32) *Kare=wa kazoku=to kurasi-te i-ru.* 'He leads his life with his family.'

If one were to assume that the physical-locative ConjP *Tōkyō=de* is an argument, then the manner AdvP *siawase-ni* and the comitative PP *kazoku=to* would have to be treated as

arguments. But then, what would be the θ -role instead of physical domain in [physical domain, agent]? In reality, the verb *kuras-u* is semantically self-contained in the sense of 'lead one's life' and does not inherently select any other argument than agent for semantic completeness. By default, anyone who is alive is leading a life. Presenting only this content by means of the predicate *kuras-* is therefore nearly vacuous in terms of information and pragmatics, so the hearer naturally demands some supplementary information such as physical domain, manner, comitative participant, etc. This is why (30) is felt to be infelicitous. Thus, the ConjP *Tōkyō=de* in *Tōkyō=de kuras-u* is best treated as a physical-locative adjunct rather than an argument. The same is true of the one-argument existential verb *ar-u* 'exist'. The clause *A=wa aru* 'A exists' is, on its own, informationally and pragmatically nearly vacuous in most cases, unless used in contexts such as *kanōsei=wa aru* 'the possibility exists'. Hence, this language characteristically supplies a domain specification of A's existence, yielding *A=wa B=de aru* 'A exists, with A's existence located in the conceptual domain of B', where the conceptual domain of existence is specified by *B=de*.

By contrast, the seemingly synonymous verb *sum-u* 'have one's residence (somewhere)' behaves differently. In the natural example in (33), if the physical-locative PP *Tōkyō=ni* 'in Tokyo' is deleted, as in (34):

(33) *Kare=wa Tōkyō=ni sun-de ir-u.* 'He has his residence in Tokyo.'

(34) **Kare=wa sun-de ir-u.* 'He has his residence.'

the result is unacceptable. (Note that the verb *sum-u* is usually translated as 'live (somewhere)'. The translation 'have one's residence' is adopted here to mirror the argument-selecting profile of *sum-u* in English.) But, unlike *kuras-u* 'lead one's life', the missing locative PP *Tōkyō=ni* in (34) cannot be substituted by either the manner AdvP *siawase=ni* 'happily' or the comitative PP *kazoku=to* 'with his family' for semantic completeness. The resultant sentences in (35) and (36) remain equally unacceptable:

(35) **Kare=wa siawase=ni sun-de ir-u.* 'He has his residence happily.'

(36) **Kare=wa kazoku=to sun-de ir-u.* 'He has his residence with his family.'

This contrast indicates that, unlike *kuras-u* 'lead one's life', *sum-u* is semantically incomplete without a locative phrase. It thus selects as an argument a physical-locative phrase specifying

the place of residence. The argument structure is [physical domain, theme], unlike *kuras-u*, whose argument structure is [agent], and the locative is constituted not by the ConjP *NP=de* — underlyingly *NP=ni-te* — but by the PP *NP=ni*.

The adjunctive status of the ConjP *Tōkyō=de* in *kare=wa Tōkyō=de kurasi-te iru* in (28), where the verb *kuras-u* does not select any argument but is nevertheless informationally and pragmatically nearly vacuous on its own, and the argumental status of the PP *Tōkyō=ni* in *kare=wa Tōkyō=ni sun-de ir-u*, where *sum-u* selects a locative phrase as an argument, are consistent with the generalisation discussed in Section 2: an argumental *NP=ni* is intrinsically selected by the predicate as semantically indispensable, whereas an adjunct *NP=ni* is extrinsic to and contingent on the predicate, hence only optionally linked either to the predicate itself or to some node within the predicate phrase; this optional linkage must generally be made overt by the adjunctive-conjunction suffix *-te* in Contemporary Japanese. It follows that there are **semantic–syntactic non-deletability** and **informational–pragmatic non-deletability**, and therefore that **simple non-deletability vs. deletability is not, by itself, a reliable diagnostic for argumenthood**.

6. Shift of focus and foregrounding of the lexical meaning 'exist' of the verb *aru*

In the construction *watasi=wa ryōsikitekina syakaizin=de aru* in (37):

- (37) *watasi=wa ryōsikitekina syakaizin=de ar-u*
 I(SUBJ)=TOP rational member of society=CONCEP-LOC-CONJ(ADJUNCT) exist-PRES
 'I exist, with my existence located in the domain of "rational member of society".'

which can be schematically represented as $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$, the existence-introducing component $E(A)$ — that is, the predicative function encoded in the verbal stem *ar-* 'exist' — is backgrounded as given information, whereas the existence-domain-specifying component $IN(evE(A), B)$ is foregrounded as the informational focus of the sentence. Furthermore, as noted in Section 2, in Contemporary Japanese the verb *aru* is more commonly used with an overt locative phrase — that is, as a two-argument existential verb, as in ***B=ni A=ga aru*** 'there is A in/at/on B', or locative verb, as in ***A=wa B=ni aru*** 'A is in/at/on B' — than as a one-argument existential verb, as in ***A=wa aru*** 'A exists', and the verb *sonzai-suru* is often preferred for this type of predication, as in ***A=wa sonzai-suru*** 'A exists'. As a result, in ordinary assertions of the

which can be represented as shown in (41), containing the two-argument state-change verb *naru* 'become', with *=ni* marking the argument GOAL:

- (41) *watasi=wa ryōsikitekina syakaizin=ni nari- -tai-T⁰Ø*
 I(SUBJ)=TOP rational member of society=GOAL(ARGUMENT) **become** want-PRES
 'I want to BE a rational member of society.'

7. From Old Japanese to Contemporary Japanese forms

In Old Japanese (OJ, 700–800), the modern formally distinct constructions *A=wa B=de aru* 'A exists, with A's existence located in the conceptual domain of B' and *A=wa B=ni aru/iru* 'A is located in the physical domain of B' would have corresponded to the seemingly identical construction *A B=ni ari*. "Dative *ni* is the general oblique case, marking both argument and non-argument oblique nominals" (Frellesvig 2010: 126), unlike in Contemporary Japanese, where *=ni* marks arguments, while *=de* — which originated from the postposition–suffix sequence *=nite* — marks adjuncts, in accordance with the diachronic description "OJ *ni* and *nite* became more specialized with *ni* being used more for arguments and *nite* more for adjuncts; from mid to late EMJ *nite* acquired the variant *de* which is still in use in contemporary NJ" (*ibid.*: 243), where EMJ and NJ abbreviate Early Middle Japanese (800–1200) and 'new Japanese' — namely, Modern Japanese, 1600– — respectively.

Thus, the former *A B=ni ari* can be analysed as an existence-introducing and existence-domain-specifying construction consisting of both the argumental structure *A ari* 'A exists' — with the verb *ari* being used as **one-argument existential predicate** — and the conceptual-locative adjunct *B=ni* '(A's existence) located in the conceptual domain of B', as shown in (42). The latter *A B=ni ari* is, on the other hand, analysable as a physical-location-specifying construction consisting solely of the argumental structure *A B=ni ari* 'A is located in the physical domain of B', in which the verb *ari* is employed as a **two-argument locative predicate** and *B=ni* constitutes the physical-locative argument, as indicated in (43):

- (42) A B=**ni** **ari-T⁰Ø**
 A(SUBJ)=TOP B=CONCEP-LOC(ADJUNCT) **exist-PRES**
 'A exists, A's existence located in the conceptual domain of B.'

- (43) A B=**ni** **ari-T⁰Ø**
 A(SUBJ)=TOP B=PHYSIC-LOC(ARGUMENT) **be located-PRES**
 'A is located in the physical domain of B.'

rather than total, or wide-scoped, in (54):

- (54) *kare=wa* *gakusei=de* (**ara-*) **-nai**-T⁰Ø
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student=CONCEP-LOC-CONJ(ADJUNCT) exist NEG-PRES
 'He does **not** exist as a student.'

(Note that in (53) and (54), the stem of the existential verb *aru* is represented as (**ara-*), since the negative form of this verb is today not the theoretically expected **ara-nai* — with the so-called *mizenkei* stem *ara-* — but obligatorily the suppletive adjective *nai*.) The more natural sentence *kare=wa gakusei=de=wa nai* in (53) — or, more colloquially, *kare=wa gakusei=dya nai*, with the contracted form =*dya* derived from the sequence =*de=wa* — does **not negate the existence of *kare* itself**, but rather **negates only *gakusei=de* as the relevant domain of *kare*'s existence**. In this way, **the particle =*wa* can mark the scope of negation in Japanese**.

Schematically, the partial negation *A=wa B=de=wa nai* in (53) — underlyingly, **A=wa B=de=wa ara-nai* — can be represented as $E(A) \wedge \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$, whereas the total negation *A=wa B=de nai* in (54) — underlyingly, **A=wa B=de ara-nai* — can be represented as $\neg(E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)) \equiv \neg E(A) \vee \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$. Although this disjunction is compatible with $\neg E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$, $E(A) \wedge \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$ or $\neg E(A) \wedge \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$, the first case is inconsistent with the conditional $\text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B) \Rightarrow E(A)$ — hence, the contrapositive $\neg E(A) \Rightarrow \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$ — and the third case, $\neg E(A) \wedge \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B) \equiv \neg E(A)$, is pragmatically infelicitous in topicalised constructions with *A=wa*, since *A=wa*, as a topicalised phrase, tends to presuppose the contextual or situational givenness — that is, the existence — of *A* and, moreover, since there are dedicated Japanese forms for existential negation such as *A=wa nai* / *i-nai* / *sonzai-si-nai*; in practice, therefore, the interpretation converges on $E(A) \wedge \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$. Hence, the former pattern in (53), which unambiguously expresses the partial negation $E(A) \wedge \neg \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$, is judged to be the more natural one.

This analysis is further supported by Kansai variety forms such as *gakusei=ya nai* and *gakusei=ya ara-hen*, which are natural and frequent and correspond closely to the standard forms *gakusei=de=wa nai* and *gakusei=dya nai*. In the former forms, the focus particle =*ya* originated from the sequence =*de=wa*, via =*dya*, and *-hen* functions as a negator, just as *-nai* does. By contrast, corresponding forms without this particle — namely, *gakusei=de nai* and *gakusei=de ara-hen* — are pragmatically infelicitous.

If =*de aru* were a single copula, then *A=wa B=de aru* would represent $BE(A, B)$, and its

negation would take the form of simple predicate negation $A=wa B=de nai$, representable as $\neg BE(A, B)$, with no $=wa$ following $=de$. **Empirically, however, $A=wa B=de nai$ is perceived as infelicitous, whereas $A=wa B=de=wa nai$ and $A=wa B=dya nai$ are preferred.** This preference for the particle $=wa$ after $=de$ is unexpected under the simple-copula analysis, but follows naturally if the sentence is decomposed as $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$, so that the logically and pragmatically most plausible interpretation is the partial negation $E(A) \wedge \neg IN(evE(A), B)$.

By contrast, the **default negation pattern of the physical-location-specifying** sentences in (55) = (23) and (56) = (24), which can both be represented as $IN(A, B)$:

- (55) sore=*wa* gakkō=*ni* ar-u
 it(SUBJ)=TOP school=PHYSIC-LOC(ARGUMENT) be located-PRES
 'It is located in the school.'
- (56) kare=*wa* gakkō=*ni* i-ru
 he(SUBJ)=TOP school=PHYSIC-LOC(ARGUMENT) be located-PRES
 'He is located in the school.'

is **total**, as indicated in (57) and (58):

- (57) sore=*wa* gakkō=*ni* (*ara-) **nai-T⁰∅**
 it(SUBJ)=TOP school=PHYSIC-LOC(ARGUMENT) be located NEG-PRES
 'It is **not** located in the school.'
- (58) kare=*wa* gakkō=*ni* i- **nai-T⁰∅**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP school=PHYSIC-LOC(ARGUMENT) be located NEG-PRES
 'He is **not** located in the school.'

Unlike the existence-introducing and existence-domain-specifying conjunctive proposition $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$, the physical-location-specifying $IN(A, B)$ is atomic and, naturally, its negation constitutes $\neg IN(A, B)$, which corresponds to (57) and (58).

On the other hand, when the PP $gakkō=ni$ in (57) and (58) is marked by $=wa$, this particle functions contrastively, as in (59) and (60), respectively, where CONTR abbreviates contrastive:

- (59) sore=*wa* gakkō=*ni=wa* (*ara-) **nai-T⁰∅**
 it(SUBJ)=TOP school=PHYSIC-LOC(ARGUMENT)=CONTR be located NEG-PRES
 'It is **not** located in the school **but somewhere else**.'
- (60) kare=*wa* gakkō=*ni=wa* i- **nai-T⁰∅**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP school=PHYSIC-LOC(ARGUMENT)=CONTR be located NEG-PRES
 'He is **not** located in the school **but somewhere else**.'

In contrast to (57) and (58), which are representable as $\neg\text{IN}(A, B)$, (59) and (60) can be represented schematically as $\neg\text{IN}(A, B) \wedge \exists x (\text{IN}(A, x) \wedge x \neq B)$ — semantically, 'A is not located in B, and there exists a physical domain x distinct from B such that A is located in x'.

The difference in default negation pattern between the existence-introducing and existence-domain-specifying construction and the physical-location-specifying one lies in the fact that the former, $\text{E}(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$, is **conjunctive**, whereas the latter, $\text{IN}(A, B)$, is **atomic**. This ultimately derives from **the status of B as an adjunct in the former and as an argument in the latter**, since if B were an argument, $\text{E}(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$ would correspond to something like $\text{EXIST-MANNER}(A, B)$, whose negation would be the total $\neg\text{EXIST-MANNER}(A, B)$.

Finally, if $=de$ *aru* were a single copular unit, partial negation with $=wa$ would necessarily take the form $*kare=wa$ *gakusei=wa* *de nai*, as in (61):

- (61) *kare=*wa* gakusei=**wa** de **nai**-T⁰Ø
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student(PRED)=CONTR COP NEG-PRES
 'He is **not** a student **but something else**.'

This ungrammaticality further supports the separability of $=de$ and *aru* and the constituency of *gakusei=de*.

9. The differences between $A=wa$ $B=de$ *aru* and $A=ga$ $B=de$ *aru*

The following table (62) provides a preliminary overview of the propositional identity and the information-structural differences between sentences of the type $A=wa$ $B=de$ *aru* and those of the type $A=ga$ $B=de$ *aru*, without attempting a full formalisation, which lies beyond the scope of this paper:

(62)

Sentence	Propositional structure	Informational structure	
		Given	New
$A=wa$ $B=de$ <i>aru</i>	$\text{E}(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$	$\text{E}(A)$	$\text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$
$A=wa$ $B=de=wa$ <i>nai</i>	$\text{E}(A) \wedge \neg\text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$	$\text{E}(A)$	$\neg\text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$
$A=wa$ $B=de=wa$ <i>naku</i> $C=wa$ $B=de$ <i>aru</i>	$\text{E}(A) \wedge \neg\text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$ $\wedge \text{E}(C) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(C), B)$	$\text{E}(A) \wedge \text{E}(C)$	$\neg\text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$ $\wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(C), B)$
$A=ga$ $B=de$ <i>aru</i>	$\text{E}(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$	$\exists x (\text{E}(x) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(x), B))$	$x = A$
$A=ga$ $B=de=wa$ <i>nai</i>	$\text{E}(A) \wedge \neg\text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$	$\exists x (\text{E}(x) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(x), B))$	$x \neq A$
$A=ga$ $B=de=wa$ <i>naku</i> $C=ga$ $B=de$ <i>aru</i>	$\text{E}(A) \wedge \neg\text{IN}(\text{evE}(A), B)$ $\wedge \text{E}(C) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(C), B)$	$\exists x (\text{E}(x) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(x), B))$	$(x \neq A) \wedge (x = C)$

Syntactically, the structure of $A=ga B=de aru$ in (62) can be represented as in (63):

$$(63) \left[\text{TP} \left[\text{NP } A_i=ga \right] \left[\text{T}' \left[\text{VP}_1 \left[\text{ConjP } B=ni-te \right] \left[\text{VP}_0 \left[\text{NP } x_i \right] \left[\text{V } ar- \right] \right] \right] \left[\text{T } -ru \right] \right] \right]$$

where x designates a trace, used here instead of the conventional notation t . In this structure, the higher VP $\left[\text{VP}_1 \left[\text{ConjP } B=ni-te \right] \left[\text{VP}_0 \left[\text{NP } x_i \right] \left[\text{V } ar- \right] \right] \right]$ conveys the given information $\exists x (E(x) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(x), B))$, whereas the **untopicalised** — and thus capable of indicating a piece of new information — NP $\left[\text{NP } A_i=ga \right]$ conveys the new information $x = A$, through the anaphoric relation of the trace $\left[\text{NP } x_i \right]$ to its antecedent $\left[\text{NP } A_i=ga \right]$. Note that the notation $\exists x$ here indicates that there exists a variable x into which a constant can be substituted as new information within the information structure. The constituents conveying given and new information are enclosed within boxes and, furthermore, those encoding new information are shaded. (The bracket notation adopted here is a descriptive representation of hierarchical constituency, and the traditional category labels are used merely as a device for visualising the structure.)

On the other hand, the structure of $A=wa B=de aru$ in (62) can be represented as in (64):

$$(64) \left[\text{TopP} \left[A_i=wa \right] \left[\text{Top}' \left[\text{TP} \left[\text{VP}_1 \left[\text{ConjP } B=ni-te \right] \left[\text{VP}_0 \left[\text{NP } x_i \right] \left[\text{V } ar- \right] \right] \right] \left[\text{T } -ru \right] \right] \left[\text{Top } Top^0 \emptyset \right] \right]$$

In this structure, the **topicalised** phrase $\left[A_i=wa \right]$ — which typically conveys a piece of given information, since it typically refers to an entity already introduced in the discourse, namely a referent already known to the addressee — and the lower VP $\left[\text{VP}_0 \left[\text{NP } x_i \right] \left[\text{V } ar- \right] \right]$ — where the verb $\left[\text{V } ar- \right]$ 'exist' provides another piece of given information, since the topicalised phrase $\left[A_i=wa \right]$ generally presupposes the existence of A — together convey the given information $E(A)$. By contrast, the ConjP $\left[\text{ConjP } B=ni-te \right]$ encodes the new information $\wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$, since a sentence conveying solely given information would be informationally vacuous. Note that, since $\text{IN}(\text{ev}E(x), B) \Rightarrow E(x)$, it follows that $\exists x (E(x) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(x), B)) \equiv \exists x \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(x), B)$; nevertheless, the logically redundant $\exists x (E(x) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(x), B))$ represents a component within the informational structure that corresponds to the syntactic–semantic structure assumed in this paper.

10. The contracted form =da

In spoken language, the contracted form =da is very often used instead of =de aru, which is

more formal and literal, as in *kare=wa gakusei=da* rather than *kare=wa gakusei=de aru*. It should be noted that this **contracted form =da** does not represent a new copular category 'be' but is a **purely phonological reduction of the postpositional–conjunctive–verbal complex =de aru**, as shown in (65):

- (65) *kare=wa* *gakusei=d* **a-T⁰Ø-Top⁰Ø**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student=CONCEP-LOC–CONJ(ADJUNCT) **exist-PRES**
 'He exists, with his existence located in the conceptual domain of "student".'

The historical change from *=de aru* to *=da*, possibly via *=dea*⁵, involves no semantic or syntactic reanalysis, but a process of phonological reduction comparable to German *in dem* → *im* 'in the' or Portuguese *de a* → *da* 'from the' or 'of the'. Just as there is no semantic necessity for *in* and *dem* to fuse into *im*, or for *de* and *a* into *da* — a phenomenon comparable to the English *in the*, *from the* or *of the* forming a single word — there is likewise no semantic motivation for *=de* and *aru* to form a SINGLE lexical item.

That said, however, the reduction of *aru* to *a* can be accounted for in informational and pragmatic terms. First, as already discussed in Sections 2 and 5, the crucial logical — though not syntactic — predicate in this construction is not the verbal predicate *ar-*, representable as $E()$, but the underlying predicate-like postposition *=ni*, representable as $IN(ev(),)$, contained within the surface postposition–conjunctive complex *=de*.

Second, the topicalised phrase *A=wa*, marked by the topicalisation particle *=wa*, generally presupposes at the discourse level the existence of *A*, namely $E(A)$. Moreover, the adjunctive-conjunction phrase *B=de* is representable as the additional conjunct $\wedge IN(ev(), B)$. When *A=wa* and *B=de* occur in succession in the string *A=wa B=de...*, the hearer is led to anticipate the full conjunctive proposition $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$. In this context, the existential verb *aru* becomes informationally redundant when it once again introduces $E(A)$.

In non-sentence-final coordinate clauses, the inflected form *ari* of *aru* in *=de ari* is often omitted, which is a natural consequence of the above anticipation. Returning to Section 1, the compound sentence *kare=wa gakusei=de, kanozyo=wa syakaizin=da* 'he (is) a student, and she is a working adult' in (5) — underlyingly, *kare=wa gakusei=de ari, kanozyo=wa syakaizin=da*

⁵ Historically, the form *=dea*, which yielded the modern *=da*, can be attested in Azuchi–Momoyama-period materials: *bonnin yorimo giūzaini fuxōzuru cotodea* '(it) is a reason for imposing a heavier guilt (on him) than on an ordinary person' (Amakusa Edition of *Esopo no fabulas*, 1593, p.475, ll.10-11, in Text Data Sets for Research on the History of Japanese).

— can be analysed as in (66):

- (66) *kare=wa* *gakusei=de* (**ari**) *kanozyo=wa* *syakaizin=d* **a-T⁰∅-Top⁰∅**
 he(SUBJ)=TOP student=LOC-CONJ (exist) she(SUBJ)=TOP working adult= LOC-CONJ exist-PRES
 'He (**exists**), with (his **existence**) located in the conceptual domain of "student",
 she **exists**, with her **existence** located in the conceptual domain of "working adult".'

The construction in (66) is an instance of zeugma, in which the inflected form *ari* of the existential verb *aru* is deleted, since, as stated in the previous paragraph, the proposition $E(kare) \wedge IN(evE(kare), gakusei)$ is predictable already at the point *kare=wa gakusei=de*, and since *ari* in *gakusei=de ari* is contextually recoverable on the basis of the structural parallelism between the two coordinate clauses. Therefore, *=de* is not an inflected form of *=da*.

Third, in a sentence in which $IN(evE(A), B)$ is presented as new information, $E(A)$ is presupposed and thus treated as given, owing to the conditional $IN(evE(A), B) \Rightarrow E(A)$. In this context, $E(A)$ is pragmatically and informationally less significant than the focus component $IN(evE(A), B)$.

It may therefore be assumed that **this low informational and pragmatic salience is reflected in the phonological reduction of *aru* to *a***. This reduction can be analysed as follows: morphologically, the [-past] tense suffix has the phonologically null allomorph /-0/ — which we designate as Tense⁰∅, abbreviated as T⁰∅ — instead of the canonical *-u* /-ru/ in *ar-u* /*ar-ru*/, yielding /*ar-0*/; phonologically, the word-final /-r/ is deleted in phonetic implementation, giving rise to the surface form *a*.

On the other hand, The reduction of the underlying *=ni-te ar-0* to the surface *=da*, via *=de ar-0*, can be accounted for by the fixed order of these concatenated morphemes and its frequency. In existence-introducing and existence-domain-specifying constructions, the morphemes *=ni*, *-te* and *ar-* — which as a whole corresponds to the schematic expression $E() \wedge IN(evE(),)$ and in which *=ni*, *-te* and *ar-* encode $IN(ev(),)$, \wedge and $E()$, respectively — is invariably ordered in this way, except in scrambling constructions — or *kakimazekōbun* in Japanese linguistics — such as *B=de watasi / watasitati / wareware=wa ari-tai* '(lit.) as B, I / we / we want to exist'.

The very high frequency of this fixed order in actual utterances is assumed to have led to the phonological reduction of *=ni-te ar-i* → *=de ar-u* → *=de-a* → *=d-a*, just as in the German and Portuguese examples mentioned above, and likewise in the contractions *si-te=i-ru* → *si-te-ru* 'be doing something' or 'have done sth.', and *si-te=sima-u* → *si-t-sima-u* → *si-t-sya-u* 'end up doing sth.' or 'do sth. inadvertently or unintentionally', as reflected in the synchronically

available colloquial forms of Contemporary Japanese.

It is not uncommon for a phonological form whose linear segmentation is no longer transparent to encode multiple meanings. In French, for instance, the present indicative first-person singular form *ai* /e/ of the verb *avoir* 'to have', as in *j'ai* 'I have' — derived from the same inflected form *habeō* /hab-ē-ō/, plausibly surfacing as [habeo:], from the Classical Latin *habēre* 'idem.' — expresses the lexical meaning 'have' in addition to a bundle of functional meanings such as [-non-assertive], [-past], [-posterior], [-anterior], [-non-participant], [-addressee] and [-plural]. Japanese =*da*, too, is nothing more than the outcome of diachronic phonological attrition: four independent morphemes =*ni*, *-te*, *ar-* and *-ru* have been worn down over time and have come to assume a simple shape =*da*.

In sum, =*da* as a whole should not be regarded as a copula in the strict sense, but rather as a **phonologically reduced surface realisation of the underlying structure =*ni-te ar-0***. In this underlying structure, =*de* — underlyingly =*ni-te* — constitutes an adjunctive postposition–conjunction complex that conjunctively specifies the conceptual domain in which the theme's existence is located, while *ar-* functions as the one-argument existential predicate and *-0* realises the phonologically null [-past] tense suffix T⁰∅. This is precisely why the following highly colloquial dialogue in (67) is possible:

(67) *Kare=tte gakusei=da yone? — Iya, gakusei=tte yū=ka, gakusei=de=mo aru=tte kanzi kana.*

'He's a student, right?' — 'Well, if you can call him a student, I'd say he's *also* a student, kind of.'

In (67), the interlocutor, recognising that the underlying structure of *gakusei=da* is *gakusei=de aru*, when asked to confirm that *kare*'s conceptual domain of existence can be identified with that of 'student', replies that it extends to other domains as well, expressed by the form *gakusei=de=mo aru*, representable as E(he) ∧ IN(evE(he), student) ∧ IN(evE(he), something else)....

11. Syntactic and logical-propositional differences between NPs with =*da*, nominal adjectives in *-da* and verbal adjectives

Japanese **nominal adjectives** (NAs), also referred to as ***na*-adjectives** due to their attributive forms ending in *-na* — the so-called *rentaikei* in Japanese linguistics — as in *yukai-na hito* 'a

pleasant person', have often been analysed as consisting of "so-called NA stems plus the so-called copula =*da*", in parallel with "NPs plus the so-called copula =*da*", as in *sore=wa yukai=da* 'it is pleasant', in parallel with *sore=wa gakkō=da* 'it is a school'.

According to Makino (2025²: 22), however, **the core of NAs lies in the NA stem in -*ni***, as in *yukai-ni* 'be pleasant' and *suki-ni* 'like'. The element *-ni* is not a postposition but the NA thematic — or, stem-forming — suffix, which functions as an indispensable morphological and semantic constituent in the formation of the NA stem. These NA stems are lexical predicates that select arguments — a theme in *yukai-ni*, and an experiencer–theme pair in *suki-ni* — just as verbal-adjective (VA) stems are, including the one-argument predicate *tanosi-ku* 'be enjoyable' with a theme and the two-argument predicate *hosi-ku* 'want' with an experiencer–theme pair. However, outside small clauses functioning as complements of cognition or perception verbs, as in *watasi=wa [sore=o yukai-ni] omot-ta / kanzi-ta* 'I found / felt [it pleasant]', such NA stems cannot function as predicates in their bare *-ni* form unlike VA stems, as in *sore=wa tanosi-ku*, **yukai-ni* 'it is enjoyable, pleasant' and *sore=wa *yukai-ni, tanosi-i* 'it is pleasant, enjoyable'.

Consequently, an NA stem forms a nominal-adjective phrase containing PRO, as in [*PRO yukai-ni*], which serves as the complement of the adjunctive conjunction *-te*, yielding a ConjP [*PRO yukai-ni-te*]. This ConjP is then adjoined to the VP headed by the existential-verb stem *ar-* within a one-argument obligatory construction, as in [*sore_i=wa t_i ar-0-0*] 'it exists', where *-0-0* represents the sequence of T⁰∅ and Top⁰∅. Only in this configuration can the NA stem function as the predicate of an independent sentence, as in [*sore_i=wa [PRO_i yukai-ni-te] t_i ar-0-0*], which surfaces as *sore=wa yukai-d-a* [*sore_i=wa [PRO_i yukai-d] t_i a-0-0*] "(lit.) it exists, being pleasant'. On the other hand, the so-called copular construction *sore=wa gakkō=d-a* '(lit.) it exists, with its existence located in the conceptual domain of "school"' can be underlyingly analysed, as already discussed, as [*sore_i=wa [gakkō=ni-te] t_i ar-0-0*], which surfaces [*sore_i=wa [gakkō=d] t_i a-0-0*].

Thus, the so-called copular sentences and the nominal-adjectival sentences share the syntactic property that they both consist of an existence-introducing, one-argument core construction combined with either an existence-domain-specifying adjunctive ConjP in the former or a state-specifying adjunctive ConjP in the latter, and can both be schematically represented as conjunctive propositions, as in (68) and (69):

(68) *Sore=wa gakkō=d-a*. [*sore_i=wa [gakkō=ni-te] t_i ar-0-0*] E(sore) ∧ IN(evE(sore), gakkō)

(69) *Sore=wa yukai-d-a*. [*sore_i=wa [PRO_i yukai-ni-te] t_i ar-0-0*] E(sore) ∧ PLEASANT(sore)

The difference is that, since the PP [*gakkō=ni*] in (68) does not constitute a lexical predicate, it does not select any argument; therefore, the adjunctive construction [*gakkō=ni-te*] does not contain PRO, unlike the adjunct [*PRO yukai=ni-te*] in the nominal-adjectival construction in (69).

By contrast, **verbal adjectives (VAs)** — also referred to as adjectives, canonical adjectives or ***i*-adjectives** due to their attributive forms ending in *-i*, as in *tanosi-i hito* 'a fun person' — form constructions in which they themselves function as the main predicate. Such constructions, as in *sore=wa tanosi-i* 'it is enjoyable', consist only of a state-specifying obligatory argumental construction without any adjunct, and thus can be represented as atomic propositions, as in (70):

(70) *Sore=wa tanosi-i.* [*sore_i=wa t_i tanosi-i-0-0*] ENJOYABLE(*sore*)

The syntactic and logical-propositional differences between (68) and (69), on the one hand, and (70), on the other, become manifest in their default negation patterns, as shown in (71) – (73):

(71) *Sore=wa gakkō=de=wa na-i.* E(*sore*) ∧ ¬IN(evE(*sore*), **gakkō**)

(72) *Sore=wa yukai=de=wa na-i.* E(*sore*) ∧ ¬PLEASANT(*sore*)

(73) *Sore=wa tanosi-ku na-i.* ¬ENJOYABLE(*sore*)

The default negation patterns of the constructions in (68) and (69) — representable as the conjunctive propositions E(*sore*) ∧ IN(evE(*sore*), *gakkō*) and E(*sore*) ∧ PLEASANT(*sore*) — are partial, namely E(*sore*) ∧ ¬IN(evE(*sore*), *gakkō*) and E(*sore*) ∧ ¬PLEASANT(*sore*), as in (71) and (72), whereas that of the construction in (70) — representable as the atomic proposition ENJOYABLE(*sore*) — is total, namely ¬ENJOYABLE(*sore*), as in (73).

It follows that the stem allomorph *at-* of the verb *ar-u* occurring in the past form *tanosi-k-at-ta*, for example, does not instantiate the one-argument existential verb *ar-* 'exist' used in both so-called copular and nominal-adjectival sentences. Rather, as stated in Makino (2025¹: 4), it is an allomorph of "the stem *ar-* from the light verb *ar-u*" inserted as a matter of formal necessity in order to concatenate the **verbal** past-tense suffix *-ta* with the **non-verbal** VA stem *tanosi-ku*, which is incompatible with the former, as in *tanosi-ku + -ta* → *tanosi-ku + ar- + -ta* → *tanosi-k-at-ta*. The default negation of this past form *tanosi-k-at-ta* is likewise total, namely *tanosi-ku na-k-a-ta*, rather than the partial negation *tanosi-ku=wa na-k-at-ta*. This demonstrates that

tanosi-ku does not constitute an adjunct forming a separate proposition and thus provides further evidence that *ar-* in this construction is not a one-argument existential verb. Note finally that the partial negation of the construction in (74) gives rise to an implication such as \wedge SOME-OTHER-STATE(sore):

(74) *Sore=wa tanosi-ku=wa na-i.* \neg ENJOYABLE(sore) \wedge SOME-OTHER-STATE(sore)

The syntactic derivation of the pseudo-copular, nominal-adjectival and verbal-adjectival constructions in (75) – (77) (= (68) – (70)) and (78) can be illustrated as follows:

(75) *Sore=wa gakkō=d-a.* '(lit.) It exists, with its existence located in the domain of "school".'

Adjunct	Core construction
[=ni]	[ar-]
→ [gakkō=ni]	→ [sore ar-]
→ [[gakkō=ni] -te]	
	→ [[[gakkō=ni] -te] [sore ar-]] (adjunct embedding)
	→ [[[[[gakkō=ni] -te] [sore ar-]] T ⁰ ∅]
	→ [[[[[[[gakkō=ni] -te] [sore ar-]] T ⁰ ∅] Top ⁰ ∅]
	→ [sore _i =wa [[[[[[[gakkō=ni] -te] [t _i ar-]] T ⁰ ∅] Top ⁰ ∅]]]
	→ <i>sore=wa gakkō=d-a</i>

As already noted in the previous section, the underlying sequences =ni-te-ar-0 and -ni-te-ar-0 surfaces as =d-a and -d-a in (75), as well as in (76) below:

(76) *Sore=wa yukai-d-a.* '(lit.) It exists, being pleasant.'

Adjunct	Core construction
[yukai-ni]	[ar-]
→ [PRO yukai-ni]	→ [sore ar-]
→ [[PRO yukai-ni] -te]	
	→ [[[PRO _i yukai-ni] -te] [sore _i ar-]] (adjunct embedding)
	→ [[[[[PRO _i yukai-ni] -te] [sore _i ar-]] T ⁰ ∅]
	→ [[[[[[[PRO _i yukai-ni] -te] [sore _i ar-]] T ⁰ ∅] Top ⁰ ∅]
	→ [sore _i =wa [[[[[[[PRO _i yukai-ni] -te] [t _i ar-]] T ⁰ ∅] Top ⁰ ∅]]]
	→ <i>sore=wa yukai-d-a</i>

(77) *Sore=wa tanosi-i*. 'It is enjoyable.'

Core construction

[*tanosi-ku*]

→ [*sore tanosi-ku*]

→ [[*sore tanosi-ku*] $T^0\emptyset$]

→ [[[*sore tanosi-ku*] $T^0\emptyset$] $Top^0\emptyset$]

→ [*sore_i=wa* [[[*t_i tanosi-ku*] $T^0\emptyset$] $Top^0\emptyset$]]

→ *sore=wa tanosi-i* (allomorphy or amalgam)

In the VA non-past form in (77), the sequence [-*ku* + $T^0\emptyset$] is morphophonologically realised as -*i*, yielding the surface form *tanosi-i* from the underlying elsewhere form *tanosi-ku*. The exponent -*i* may therefore be analysed either as a contextual allomorph -*i* of the VA thematic suffix -*ku* in the non-past environment or, alternatively, as an amalgamated realisation of the sequence [-*ku* + $T^0\emptyset$], as stated in Makino (2025¹: 14).

(78) *Sore=wa tanosi-k-at-ta*. 'It was enjoyable.'

Core construction

[*tanosi-ku*]

→ [*sore tanosi-ku*]

→ [[*sore tanosi-ku*] -*ta*]

→ [[*sore tanosi-ku*] *ar-* -*ta*] (light-verb-stem insertion)

→ [[[*sore tanosi-ku*] *ar-* -*ta*] $Top^0\emptyset$]

→ [*sore_i=wa* [[[*t_i tanosi-ku*] *ar-* -*ta*] $Top^0\emptyset$]]

→ *sore=wa tanosi-k-at-ta*

In the analysis of the VA past form in (78), the choice between the non-past $T^0\emptyset$, realised as -*0*, and the past suffix -*ta* is treated as a paradigmatic selection made at a single derivational stage, since the [-past] -*0* and the [+past] -*ta* constitute a paradigm whose terms acquire linguistic value solely through their opposition at the same point of speech. When the past suffix -*ta* is selected, it proves incompatible with non-verbal predicates such as *tanosi-ku*, thereby triggering the insertion of the light verb stem *ar-* as a repair strategy. Then, the stem-final vowel -*u* of the suffix -*ku* is deleted before *ar-*, together with the assimilation of *ar-* to *at-* before -*ta*.

Finally, the more abstract pseudo-copular, nominal-adjectival and verbal-adjectival constructions corresponding to (75) – (77) — namely, $A=wa\ B=d-a$, $A=wa\ B-d-a$ and $A=wa\ B-i$, where A designates an NP and B designates an NP, an NA radical and VA radical, respectively — can be schematically represented as in (79) – (81):

(79) $A=wa\ B=d-a$: $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$ (e.g. *sore=wa gakkō=d-a*)

(80) $A=wa\ B-d-a$: $E(A) \wedge B-ni(A)$ (e.g. *sore=wa yukai-d-a*)

(81) $A=wa\ B-i$: $B-ku(A)$ (e.g. *sore=wa tanosi-i*)

12. Classical Latin *esse*, Japanese *ari/aru* and Old English *Wesan/Bēon* — an exploratory note

Japanese is not the only language that employs a one-argument existential verb in a copula-like way. In Classical Latin, like Japanese, the default — namely, the most unmarked — one-argument existential verb was employed to encode a relation between an entity and its specification as to what it is. In Latin, the verb *esse* 'to exist; to be' was used both as a one-argument existential verb and as a so-called copula, as exemplified in *dī sunt* 'the gods exist'⁶ with a topicalised definite subject *dī* and with no locative phrase, and *dī testēs sunt* 'the gods are witnesses'.

In the latter construction, the NP *testēs* 'witnesses' is traditionally analysed as a *copular* predicate nominative, whereas here it is proposed that this NP may instead be analysed as an *appositive predicate nominative to the subject* NP *dī* 'the gods', marked by the same nominative case, likewise as in the following example: *dēfendī rem pūblicam adulēscēns, nōn dēseram senex* 'I, as a young man, defended the republic, I, as an old man, shall not desert it' (Cic. *Phil.* 2.118). In its primitive sense, the construction *dī testēs sunt* can thus be interpreted as

⁶ Cicero, *De divinatione* 2.49 contains a clear example of the one-argument existential *esse* 'exist' with no locative phrase and with a topicalised subject NP *dī* at a clause-initial position: *nōn igitur dī sunt* 'therefore **the gods do not exist**'. In a Stoic argument, the NP *dī* is first introduced as a discourse referent in the protasis *sī sunt dī ...* 'if there are gods ...' or 'if gods exist ...'. It is then maintained as a null subject *pro* along a chain of coordinated clauses. The conclusion *nōn igitur dī sunt* 'therefore the gods do not exist' then restates *dī* overtly at the point of inference, where it is naturally interpreted as referential given information. Thus, the constructed example *dī sunt* 'the gods exist' here is likely to be acceptable in this sense. On the other hand, the clause *dī testēs sunt* is borrowed from T. Livius's *Ab urbe condita* 35.19: ... *pater Hamilcar et dī testēs sunt* '... my father Hamilcar and the gods are witnesses'.

'the gods, being witnesses, exist' or 'the gods, as witnesses, exist', representable as $\text{EXIST}(\text{d}\bar{\text{i}}) \wedge \text{PRED}(\text{d}\bar{\text{i}}, \text{test}\bar{\text{e}}\text{s})$, where PRED abbreviates 'predication' and will be more simply abbreviated as P below. If the initial conjunct $\text{E}(\text{d}\bar{\text{i}})$ is deleted, the remaining proposition $\text{P}(\text{d}\bar{\text{i}}, \text{test}\bar{\text{e}}\text{s})$ will constitute what is traditionally described as a copula. (It should be noted that the term "appositive predicate nominative" is used here for the nominative nominal *testēs* in *dī testēs sunt*, which is analysed as predicative apposition rather than as a copular complement.)

In Classical Latin, however, the $\text{E}(\text{A})$ component in the conjunctive proposition $\text{E}(\text{A}) \wedge \text{P}(\text{A}, \text{B})$ appears to have remained present, albeit typically backgrounded, as in the Japanese structure $\text{E}(\text{A}) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{evE}(\text{A}), \text{B})$ discussed in Sections 5 and 10, since, to express 'to want to be/become', the state-change verb *fierī* 'to become' tended to be used rather than *esse*, as in *augur posteā fierī voluī, quod anteā neglēxeram* '(lit.) later I wanted to become an augur, having previously neglected it' (Cic. *Fam.* 15.4), as opposed to *cupiō, patrēs cōnscrīptī, mē esse clēmentem* '(lit.) I desire, senators, to exist as merciful' (Cic. *Catil.* 1.4). This opposition can be schematically represented as in:

(82) *A B fierī cupit/vult.* 'A wants to **be** B.': A WANT [BECOME(A, B)]

(83) *A B esse cupit/vult.* 'A wants to **exist as** B.': A WANT [E(A) \wedge P(A, B)]

The relation between (82) and (83) is closely paralleled by the following opposition between (84) and (85) in Japanese, discussed in Section 6:

(84) *A=wa B=ni nari-tai.* 'A wants to **be** B.': A WANT [BECOME(A, B)]

(85) *A=wa B=de ari-tai.* 'A wants to **exist as** B.': A WANT [E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)]

In Classical Latin, the tendency to use *fierī* 'to become' rather than *esse* to express 'to want to be' is compatible with the view that, even in its copula-like use, the component $\text{E}(\text{A})$ still remained present. Thus, Japanese and Classical Latin share the commonalities in (86) and (87):

(86) They employ existing linguistic resources in encoding a relation between an entity and its specification as to what it is.

(87) One of those resources is the default one-argument existential verb — namely, *ar-u* in

Japanese and *esse* in Classical Latin.

On the other hand, they differ in (88) – (90):

(88) The other resources differ — namely, the conceptual-locative postposition =*ni* and the adjunctive-conjunction suffix *-te* in Japanese, and predicative apposition and agreement in Classical Latin.

(89) In Classical Latin, the component $E(A)$ could, in principle, be deleted from $E(A) \wedge P(A, B)$ without syntactic and logical difficulty in predicating B of A , thereby yielding a genuine copula $P(A, B)$, as in $E(A) \wedge P(A, B) \rightarrow P(A, B)$ — even though, in practice, $E(A)$ does not appear to have been deleted.

(90) In Japanese, by contrast, the component $E(A)$ cannot, as a matter of syntactic and logical structure, be deleted from $E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$, since, if $E(A)$ were deleted, $A=wa$ $B=de$ *aru* would be representable as $\text{IN}(\text{ev}(\), B)$ through the deletion of its existential meaning from *ar-*, which would be logically incomplete, and syntactically inadequate since A would not be assigned any θ -role by the semantically bleached *ar-*.

Later, the deletion of the $E(A)$ component from *esse* — that is, $E(A) \wedge P(A, B) \rightarrow P(A, B)$ — may be analysed as having given rise to a genuinely copular use $P(A, B)$. In parallel its existential use $E(A)$ may have receded, with other expressions of $E(A)$ subsequently developing in the Romance languages. Finally, it is suggestive that **the English copula *be* — in Old English, *wesan/bēon* — was used, like Latin *esse* and Japanese *ari/aru*, as the default one-argument existential verb**, as in *þa hwīle þe he wæs* 'while he existed' (Thorpe 1865: 167, l.9) [= *ðā hwīle ðe hē wæs*]; *he bið á wesende* 'he is ever existent' (Morris 1880: 19, ll.25–26) [= *hē bið ā wesende*]⁷.

⁷ See also Stevick (1992: 149). In Hall (1916), the verbs that include a sense glossed as "exist" are *bēon* (2), *faran* (8), *libban* (3), *standan* (11), *wunian* (4), where the numerals in parentheses indicate the sense number under which "exist" is listed. The other verb corresponding — alongside *bēon* — to Modern English *be*, namely *wesan*, is glossed only as "to be" and "happen" in Hall, though the entry contains a cross-reference "v. also *bēon*". When these verbs are examined in Bosworth & Toller (1898), *bēon* is defined (*ibid.*: 85) as "BEÓN [bión], ...To BE, exist, become; esse, fieri", with "exist" appearing as the second sense, whereas *faran* 'go', *libban* 'live', *standan* 'stand' have no 'exist' sense at all, their basic meanings being those given in single quotation marks here. *Wunian* has the basic meanings "dwell" and "remain" and only under section III does it include "exist", which indicates that 'exist' is not its primary

13. Conclusion

In summary, **Japanese has no genuine copula — that is, =da is not be**. Instead, Japanese is a **language that has employed existence, conjunction and location to encode, compositionally, a relation between an entity and its specification as to what it is**. The function of =da and its non-contracted form =de aru is to indicate that something **exists** and that this existence is **conjunctively** specified as **located in a conceptual domain** defined by a category. Japanese linguistically encodes $E(A) \wedge IN(evE(A), B)$ through =ni, -te and ar-, whereas any interpretation in terms of $A = B$ or $A \in B$ arises as a derived meta-level inference. Thus, treating =da as be may be practical for pedagogical, translational and surface-level purposes, but **the Japanese grammatical system contains no primitive corresponding to be**.

Syntactically and semantically, the construction $A=wa B=de aru$ consists of an existence-introducing, one-argument obligatory construction [$A=wa aru$] 'A exists' combined with an existence-domain-specifying adjunctive construction [$B=de$] — underlyingly [$B=ni-te$] — meaning 'with (A's existence) located in the conceptual domain of B' or, more practically, 'and it is as B'. In this construction, the most crucial logical — albeit not syntactic — predicate is not the verbal stem ar- that introduces A's existence, but rather the predicate-like conceptual-locative postposition =ni within the postposition–conjunction complex =de, which locates A's existence in the conceptual domain of B.

Consequently, treating =da, or its non-contracted form =de aru, as a single copula is structurally problematic. The form =de aru is more appropriately analysed as an **existence-and-domain complex**, consisting of the one-argument existential verb aru 'exist' and the predicate-like conceptual-locative postposition =ni 'in' plus the adjunctive-conjunction suffix -te 'and', which together surface as =de and conjunctively specify the conceptual domain in which the existence of the theme is located. The more colloquial form =da is a phonologically contracted — though pragmatically and informationally motivated — form corresponding to the more formal and literal =de aru.

sense. Finally, for *wesan*, which together with *bēon* constitutes the Modern English verb *be*, Bosworth and Toller provide the crucial description (*ibid.*: 1210): "*wesan*; p. *wæs*, pl. *wáron* *To be*:— *Wesan* and *beón fore*, Wrt. Voc. ii. 34, 61. I. as an independent verb, (1) denoting existence *to be, exist*:— *Wesendum, beóndum existentibus*, Wrt. Voc. ii. 32, 63. (a) of animate objects, *to exist, live*". This interpretation is consistent with later scholarship: Mateo Mendaza, R. (2021: 95): "*beon* and *wesan* are purely existential verbs"; Cichosz et al. (2022: 87): No.1 *wesan* (translation *to be*); No.2 *beon* (translation *to be*) in "Table 12. 15 most frequent Old English non-lexical verbs". On the basis of the evidence reviewed above, it may be concluded that the default existential verb in Old English was *wesan/bēon*.

Thus, through the above morphosyntactic and semantic analysis, it has been possible to account, by means of a single, consistent principle — namely, the **introduction of existence by [NP₁ ar-]** and the **conjunctive specification of the conceptual domain of existence by [NP₂=ni-te] surfacing as [NP₂=de]**, schematically representable as the conjunctive proposition **E(NP₁) ∧ IN(evE(NP₁), NP₂), not reducible to the atomic BE(NP₁, NP₂)** — for:

- Morphosyntactic separability of *de* and *aru* in *=de aru*
- Syntactic and prosodic constituency of *=de* and the NPs preceding it
- Prosodic-word boundary between *=de* and *aru*
- Contextually optional omission of *aru* in *=de aru*
- Evidence for analysing *=de* as an adjunct-marking postposition–conjunction complex *=ni-te* that functions as an eventuality-domain specifier \wedge (ev(), NP)
- Foregrounding of the lexical meaning 'exist' of the verb *aru*
- Grounds on which the Japanese desiderative *=de ari-tai* is not equivalent to the English *to want to be*
- Diachronic split from Old to Modern Japanese between $A B=ni ari \rightarrow A B=nite ari \rightarrow A=wa B=de aru$ and $A B=ni ari \rightarrow A=wa B=ni aru/iru$
- Evidence that the default negation of $A=wa B=de aru$ is not the total $A=wa B=de nai$ but the partial $A=wa B=de=wa nai$
- Syntactic and information-structural differences between $A=wa B=de aru$ and $A=ga B=de aru$
- Underlying structure *=ni-te ar-T^o∅* surfacing as *=d-a-T^o∅*
- Pragmatic and informational motivation for the phonological reduction *aru* → *a* in *=da*
- Commonalities and differences between the so-called copular, nominal-adjectival and verbal-adjectival constructions

Put differently, to maintain the claim that *=da* is *be*, one would have to assume that the inherent meanings of *=ni*, *-te* and *ar-* — which together still autonomously underlie *=da* — have been

eliminated or, alternatively, somehow changed into another meaning. One would then further need to explain when these meanings were eliminated or changed, why they were eliminated or changed, at what grammatical level they were eliminated or changed, and why meanings that are assumed to have been eliminated or changed nevertheless become foregrounded in desiderative constructions, exert structural effects under negation, create prosodic boundaries and maintain diachronic continuity.

Finally, while the present study reinterprets *=da* and *=de aru* as a postposition–conjunction–verb complex encoding $E(A) \wedge \text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$ rather than a copular predicate representable as $\text{BE}(A, B)$, this proposal is not intended to invalidate previous research conducted within the copular framework. Much of the empirical and descriptive work on so-called copular sentences remains valuable and can be accommodated within the present account as analyses of the $\text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$ component, that is, as investigations into how the conceptual domain of existence is structured. In this respect, the present analysis may be regarded not as a rejection of the copular tradition but as an attempt to extend it by situating its insights within a broader model of Japanese predicational structure. Furthermore, the interaction between the existence-introducing component $E(A)$ and the domain-specifying component $\text{IN}(\text{ev}E(A), B)$, which has received relatively little explicit attention in previous research, may provide a useful perspective for future studies on how these two semantic components relate to one another in information structure, negation and discourse.

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